

QUIZ**LAST NAME: OKELLO****FIRST NAME: PATRICK****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **How should a student or a researcher define a research question and analyze the task to meet an academic essay's aim?**
 - Must exactly understand what the question requires and identify the keywords and clarify the necessary approach.¹**
 - Write down everything known about the topic from all known sources to form a basis for understanding the question.
 - Analyze the available materials, but do not waste time answering the essay question as the answers can come later.
 - No need for the question to be precise; it is more important to gather enough compelling evidence for readers to make meaning for themselves.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

2. **Which of the following is true regarding the formatting differences between notes and bibliography?**

- Notes are indented like other paragraphs, while bibliographies have a hanging indentation.²**
- A bibliography is indented the same way as a note citation.
- Commas dominate the punctuation marks in a bibliography.
- Notes are punctuated mostly with periods.
- Publication information is put in parenthesis for bibliography, unlike for notes.

3. **New researchers and students often face challenges in choosing a research topic. To reduce this dilemma, one should strongly consider which one of the following when selecting a research topic.**

- An area of his or her interest and the job in mind.³**
- The interest of the supervisor as this would make supervision easier.
- The current dominant topic being discussed in any field if one can collect data on it.
- Choose a topic in an area that is likely to be funded even if one has little or no interest.

4. **In which of the below situations is the use of quotation marks for intext citation not recommended?**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 93.

³ Ibid., 19.

- When the quotation is long with over four lines (block quotation).⁴**
- When the quotation is long, but you do not want to indent it.
- When you have paraphrased using the exact words and style of the author.
- When an authority figure says something that can help persuade readers towards your argument and want it to stand out.
5. **Which of the following best describes the goal of sound academic research?**
- Must ask a question worth asking, find answers that can be supported with good reasons, find reliable evidence to support the reasons, and be well revised until those mentioned above have been achieved.⁵**
- It must be new and ground-breaking to show that the student is among the best.
- Must be quick and easy to implement irrespective of the usefulness of its findings and compliance with set rules.
- Must look for answers; evidence may not be necessary as readers can always look for them on their own.
6. **Which of the following best describes the notes-bibliography style of citation?**
- In notes-bibliography style, superscripts placed at the end of a sentence or clause signal the sources' use. The sources are then**

⁴ Ibid., 208.

⁵ Ibid., 18.

cited in correspondingly numbered notes at the bottom or end of the page/chapter.⁶

- The use of superscript in a citation is now outdated and not practiced.
- Superscripts are always put before any punctuation mark in the text.
- After paraphrasing, there is no use of superscript in notes-bibliography.

7. Which of the listed options best describes a literature review?

- It is the systematic identification, location, and analysis of materials related to a research problem. Such materials include books, journals, articles, abstracts, reviews, monographs, and others.⁷**
- A compilation of all materials related to a research topic
- A review of specific evidence that supports a point of view in research, not against it.
- None of the above.

8. Which of the following best explains what a research methodology is?

- Methodology refers to how research proceeds and encompasses a range of logistical, relational, ethical, and credibility issues.⁸**
- Systematic steps in data collection and analysis.
- A compilation of data collection methods used in research.

⁶ Ibid., 90.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. Edited by Vicki Knight, Sean Connelly, Lauren Habib, Kristen Gibson, and Heather Jefferson (California: Sage Publications, 2008), 46.

⁸ Ibid., 73.

Steps in the review of specific evidence in support of a point of view in research.

9. **Which of the options below best describes Anderson's Behavioral Modal of health service use?**

Three characteristics influence the utilization of health services by people. These factors are Predisposing, enabling, and need characteristics.⁹

Anderson's model considers only predisposing characteristics in the utilization of health services.

Anderson's model considers only needs and predisposing characteristics in the utilization of health services.

Enabling characteristics are no longer part of Anderson's Behavioral Model of the utilization of health care services.

10. **In notes-bibliography, which of the following titles are not italicized but put in quotation marks?**

Titles of smaller entries such as chapters, unpublished works, thesis, and articles¹⁰

Titles of major books and journals

Titles of major books only

None of the above options is correct.

⁹ Kiswendsida Aida Sawadogo, "Universal Coverage in Developing Countries: A Summative Evaluation of Maternal Policies in Ghana and Burkina Faso" (Dr.PH diss., Georgia Southern University, 2017), 66.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 111-16.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. Edited by Vicki Knight, Sean Connelly, Lauren Habib, Kristen Gibson, and Heather Jefferson. California: Sage Publications, 2008.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.
- Sawadogo, Kiswendsida Aida. "Universal Coverage in Developing Countries: A Summative Evaluation of Maternal Policies in Ghana and Burkina Faso." Dr.PH diss., Georgia Southern University, 2017. Accessed February 14, 2021. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Universal-Coverage-in-Developing-Countries%3A-A-of-in-Sawadogo/5620e71338ed70be92fec2762333a5cca4fccc9>

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